

Association between Metabolic Syndrome and Men with Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms: An Observational Study from Eastern Indian Men Cohort

Prabhat Kumar¹, Shashi Prakash², Vijay Kumar³, Ravikant Sinha⁴, Ahshan Ahmad⁵, Rajesh Tiwari⁶

¹Consultant Urologist, Aurangabad Urology & Gynae Centre, Bihar, India

²Urology Resident, Department of Urology, I.G.I.M.S., Patna, Bihar, India

³H.O.D., Department of Urology, I.G.I.M.S., Patna, Bihar, India

⁴Urology Resident, Department of Urology, PARAS HMRI Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Urology, I.G.I.M.S., Patna, Bihar, India

⁶Professor, Department of Urology, I.G.I.M.S., Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-08-2023 / Revised: 23-09-2023 / Accepted: 18-10-2023

Corresponding Author: Ravikant Sinha

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objectives: The study sought to establish the manifestation of metabolic syndrome with lower urinary tract symptoms in a cohort of men from Eastern India.

Methods: This observational investigation, carried out at Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical sciences, Patna, India, for nearly 2 years, involved 210 men aged 40 and above with LUTS in East India. Data, including blood biomarkers and lifestyle factors, was collected to evaluate the connection of metabolic syndrome with lower urinary tract symptoms.

Results: In the study consisting of 210 aging males from East India, it was noted that around 39.5% of the participants showed metabolic syndrome with an average age of 64.5 years. The major components of the metabolic syndrome recorded in this study were elevated fasting blood sugar (65.23%), waist circumference (60%), and lower serum HDL (59.04%). Metabolic syndrome also correlates with higher BMI, IPSS Score, and more severe LUTS, particularly in voiding. Furthermore, patients with metabolic syndrome exhibited significantly larger prostate sizes (44.55cc vs. 33.44cc, $p < 0.0001$). Positive relationships were observed among metabolic syndrome components and LUTS, with prominent associations in voiding and storage scores.

Conclusion: This study underscores a significant connection between metabolic syndrome and the risk of Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms in men from East India.

Keywords: Metabolic Syndrome, Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms, Voiding, Male patients.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Metabolic syndrome is a major health issue of significant global implications, owing its strong link with heightened cardiovascular and non-cardiovascular mortality [1]. This syndrome comprises various health ailments such as impaired metabolism of glucose, abdominal obesity, low HDL levels, arterial hypertension, and hypertriglyceridemia, which collectively raise the likelihood of getting cardiac diseases and type 2 diabetes mellitus [2-8]. Moreover, this syndrome is also linked with other ailments, such as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), urolithiasis, microvascular ailments, obstructive sleep apnea, and polycystic ovarian syndrome [3]. While these health conditions are commonly seen in patients having metabolic syndrome, the presence of certain comorbidities are often seen in males. These

include erectile dysfunction, hypogonadism, psychological issues, and infertility [5, 9, 10].

In geriatric men, lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) are frequently encountered, and this is primarily attributed to the increased likelihood of benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) in this age group [11]. Numerous epidemiological findings also suggest a potential connection between prostatic diseases, particularly LUTS and metabolic syndrome. LUTS arising as a result of BPH affects a significant percentage of men aged 40 and above and is linked to an enhanced risk of fractures, diminished lifestyle factors, and mental health disorders, all of which impede routine activities [11,12].

In recent time, evidence based on clinical and preclinical findings suggest a probable influence of

metabolic imbalances in BPH growth, aggravation of LUTS, and prostate enlargement [13-17]. An early study dating back to 1966 also hinted the involvement of hypertension and diabetes in the pathology behind the enlargement of the prostate [18]. Subsequent studies, such as the one by Nandeeshia et al., identified HDL-cholesterol levels and insulin as negative and positive predictors of the enlargement of prostate [19]. In another study involving obese males without diabetes, positive relationship was noted between waist circumference, body mass index, and prostate volume [20]. These findings have also been recently supported by the study conducted by Muller et al. [21].

The current investigation intends to assess the relationship between metabolic syndrome and LUTS in males aged 40 and above. The primary focus was on examining all components of metabolic syndrome, and to explore the interrelationships to offer a better understanding of the disease.

Methods

This present study involved 210 male patients aged 40 and above with LUTS and getting treatment at the outpatient department of urology at Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical sciences, Patna, India from January 2017 to November 2018. Participants with prostate carcinoma, urethral stricture, urinary tract infections, psychological disorders, and who have undergone major pelvic or spinal surgery or pelvic radiation were excluded from this observational study.

In the present investigation, all the participants were subjected to a thorough examination consisting of a detailed medical history, clinical examinations, and other standard tests. These included routine blood tests, fasting blood sugar analysis, complete urinalysis, lipid profile examination, serum creatinine assessment, and imaging studies like ultrasound of the kidneys, ureters, and bladder (USG KUB). Additionally, anthropometric attributes of the patients such as

weight, height, and waist circumference were recorded, along with blood pressure. Waist circumference was specifically gauged at two points: at the level of the umbilicus and over the iliac wings. Furthermore, to assess the lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS), participants completed the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) questionnaire, with scores categorized into mild, moderate, and severe symptomatic groups.

The criteria established by The National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III (NCEP ATP III) was used for prognosis of metabolic syndrome. Patients showing positive for 3 or more specific criteria were confirmed to have metabolic syndrome. The criteria involved under this are waist circumference > 102 cm in men, blood triglyceride levels \geq 150 mg/dl, HDL cholesterol levels < 40 mg/dl in men, fasting blood glucose levels \geq 100 mg/dl, and blood pressure \geq 130/85 mm Hg.

Statistical Methods: The data was analyzed using SPSS 18, with categorical data being depicted as percentages. Student t-tests or chi-square tests were used to address the differences between the baseline characteristics of the cohort, with a significance of $p < 0.05$.

Results

Out of the 210 patients, the most common age group was identified to be the 61 to 70 years (32.85%). The average BMI was 28.57 kg/m², with around 30 % of the participants enrolled for this study were classified as obese. Based on the initial clinical tests, the overall incidence rates of metabolic syndrome were identified to be 39.5%, with elevated fasting blood sugar (65.23%), elevated waist circumference (60%), and lower serum HDL (59.04%) being the most frequently observed components. Concerning lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS), the mean IPSS score was 10.22, with 37.13% experiencing moderate symptoms and 9.04% experiencing severe symptoms (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic data of the patients participating in this study

Characteristics	Mean values
Average age (in years)	64.5
40-50	34 (16.19 %)
51-60	59 (28.09 %)
61-70	69 (32.85 %)
71-80	48 (22.85 %)
Average BMI (in kg/m³)	28.57
Patients with obesity	63 (30 %)
Patients with metabolic syndrome	83 (39.5 %)
Components of metabolic syndrome, n (%)	
Elevated fasting blood sugar	137 (65.20 %)
Elevated waist circumference	126 (60 %)

Lowered serum HDL	124 (59.04 %)
Mean waist circumference	108.42
Mean fasting blood sugar	103.56
Mean serum HDL	48.79
Patients with elevated blood pressure	114 (54.28 %)
Patients with elevated triglycerides	122 (58.09 %)
Mean IPSS Score	10.22
Prevalence of Moderate LUTS	37.13%
Prevalence of Severe LUTS	9.04%
Mean Voiding Score	5.47
Mean Storage Score	4.42
Voiding Score \geq 5	98 (46.66 %)
Storage Score \geq 4	118 (56.19 %)
Mean Prostate Size (in cc)	37.83
Mean Post Void Residual Urine (in ml)	32.58
Mean Maximum Flow Rate (in ml/second)	15.4

Discussion

The increasing prevalence of metabolic syndrome has become a global concern owing to its association with the worldwide rise in obesity and diabetes [22]. In the United States, the identified age-adjusted incidence rates of patients with metabolic syndrome was 23.7%, with rates showing a direct relationship with age, reaching 44% in individuals aged 60 to 69 years [22]. Similarly, another study in the USA also indicated a metabolic syndrome incidence of 35.1%, rising to 51.5% in men aged over 60 years [23]. The present study's observation pertaining to the occurrence rates of metabolic syndrome is also high in the elderly cohort (61-70 age group) with an incidence rate of 39.5%, aligning with these trends shown by the earlier studies [22,23].

Despite India's recognition as the "diabetic capital of the world", limited data is available on the occurrence rates of metabolic syndrome in the Indian population [24]. Moreover, existing studies have reported varying incidence rates, such as 24.9 % in males and 42.3 % in females, and 40.9 % in the eastern Indian population [24,25]. These results closely match with the outcomes identified in the present study which indicates that 39.5 % of the participants have metabolic syndrome.

The probable link of metabolic syndrome, with LUTS and benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), has also gained interest in the recent decades [26-28]. Epidemiological evidences suggest a possible link exists connecting metabolic syndrome with an elevated risk of LUTS, as indicated by studies such as NHANES III and the BACH survey [28,29]. In the current study, a positive relationship was noted between metabolic syndrome and higher IPSS, storage score, and voiding score, indicating more frequent and severe LUTS symptoms in men with metabolic syndrome. However, no statistical significance was observed in this context. This finding, however, contrasts the results from some

Asian studies which suggest a more complex relationship and a negative relationship between BPH-LUTS and metabolic syndrome [30,31].

The relationship between metabolic syndrome and prostate size is another area of interest, with studies reporting a positive connection, thereby supporting the notion that BPH is one important aspect of metabolic syndrome [32]. The findings from the current investigation coincided with these findings as a significantly larger prostate size was noted in patients with metabolic syndrome.

On examining the individual aspects of metabolic syndrome, significant associations between triglyceride levels, serum HDL, blood pressure, prostate size, and waist circumference was noted, that is in line with existing literature [32]. Another important component covered in this study was obesity. While a few studies indicate direct relationships between obesity and BPH, others have shown conflicting results [33-35]. In this investigation, a positive link was observed between prostate size and BMI, indicating a potential link between obesity and BPH.

Existing literature has shown that lifestyle interventions, such as enhanced physical activity and weight loss, lower the occurrence rates of BPH or LUTS [36]. However, despite this, the impact of managing metabolic syndrome on LUTS and BPH remains an open question with multiple areas to be addressed upon. In this context, the present study offers a significant contribution to the ongoing work correlating metabolic syndrome with LUTS and BPH. [37,38] While the revelations of this study are consistent with the previous findings, further research is required to investigate the long-term impact of lifestyle management and other therapeutic interventions in management of metabolic syndrome in patients with LUTS and BPH.

Conclusion

The current study reveals a prominent connection between metabolic syndrome and the risk of lower urinary tract symptoms/benign prostatic hyperplasia (LUTS/BPH) in geriatric men. Dyslipidemia, particularly high levels of triglyceride levels and low levels of high-density lipoproteins, have emerged as major contributors to this link with BPH, emphasizing the importance of studying these parameters for proper diagnosis and therapeutic intervention. Furthermore, this study also underscores the effectiveness of early treatment for metabolic syndrome, which can thereby promote a healthy lifestyle to lessen the impact of LUTS/BPH in the geriatric population.

Limitations

The study is limited by the absence of certain potential confounders like educational status and income, and the inability to establish causal relationships without prospective cohort studies.

References

1. Isra A, Khurana L. Obesity and the metabolic syndrome in developing countries. *J. Clin. Endocrinol Metab.* 2008; 93.
2. Corona G, Rastrelli G, Morelli A et al. Hypogonadism and metabolic syndrome. *J Endocrinol Invest* 2011; 34: 557–67.
3. Cornier MA, Dabelea D, Hernandez TL et al. The metabolic syndrome *Endocr Rev* 2008; 29 :777–822.
4. Eckel RH, Alberti KG, Grundy SM, Zimmet PZ. The metabolic syndrome *Lancet* 2010; 16: 181–3.
5. Corona G, Rastrelli G, Vignozzi L, Mannucci E, Maggi M. Testosterone, cardiovascular disease and the metabolic syndrome. *Best Pract Res ClinEndocrinolMetab* 2011; 25: 337–53.
6. Corona G, Mannucci E, Forti G, Maggi M. Following the common association between testosterone deficiency and diabetes mellitus, can testosterone be regarded as a new therapy for diabetes? *Int J Androl* 2009; 32: 431–41.
7. Corona G, Monami M, Rastrelli G et al. Type 2 diabetes mellitus and testosterone: a meta-analysis study. *Int J Androl* 2011; 34: 528–40.
8. Alberti KG, Eckel RH, Grundy SM et al. Harmonizing the metabolic syndrome: a joint interim statement of the International Diabetes Federation Task Force on Epidemiology and Prevention; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute; American Heart Association; World Heart Federation; International Atherosclerosis Society; and International Association for the Study of Obesity. *Circulation* 2009; 120:1640–5.
9. Yadav, S., Gupta, D. K., Patil, P. H., Tiwari, A., & Soni, P. To Study the Pharmacotherapy of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 Patient in Echo Health Care & Research Centre, Indore". *Jour Med Resh and Health Sci*, 2023; 6(2): 23 89–2397.
10. Corona G, Mannucci E, Ricca V et al. The age-related decline of testosterone is associated with different specific symptoms and signs in patients with sexual dysfunction. *Int J Androl* 2009; 32:720–8.
11. Lotti F, Corona G, DegliInnocenti S et al. Seminal, ultrasound and psychobiological parameters correlate with metabolic syndrome in male members of infertile couples. *Andrology* 2013; 1: 229–39.
12. Engstrom G, Henningsohn L, Steineck G et al. Self-assessed health, sadness and happiness in relation to the total burden of symptoms from the lower urinary tract. *BJU Int* 2005;95:810–5
13. Parsons JK, Mougey J, Lambert L et al. Lower urinary tract symptoms increase the risk of falls in older men. *BJU Int* 2009; 104: 63–8.
14. Kupelian V, McVary KT, Kaplan SA et al. Association of lower urinary tract symptoms and the metabolic syndrome: results from the Boston area community health survey. *J Urol* 2013; 189 (Suppl.): S107–14.
15. D Nunzio C, Aronson W, Freedland SJ, Giovannucci E, Parsons JK. The correlation between metabolic syndrome and prostatic diseases. *EurUrol* 2012; 61: 560–70.
16. Gacci M, Eardley I, Giuliano F et al. Critical analysis of the relationship between sexual dysfunctions and lower urinary tract symptoms due to benign prostatic hyperplasia. *EurUrol* 2011; 60: 809-25.
17. Gacci M, Vignozzi L, Sebastianelli A et al. Metabolic syndrome and lower urinary tract symptoms: the role of inflammation. *Prostate Cancer Prostatic Dis* 2013; 16: 101–6.
18. Vignozzi L, Morelli A, Sarchielli E et al. Testosterone protects from metabolic syndrome-associated prostate inflammation: an experimental study in rabbit. *J Endocrinol* 2012; 212: 71–84.
19. Bourke JB, Griffin JP. Hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and blood groups in benign prostatic hypertrophy. *Br J Urol* 1966; 38: 18–23.
20. Nandeesh H, Koner BC, Dorairajan LN, Sen SK. Hyperinsulinemia and dyslipidemia in non-diabetic benign prostatic hyperplasia. *Clin Chim Acta* 2006; 370: 89–93
21. Muller RL, Gerber L, Moreira DM et al. Obesity is associated with increased prostate growth and attenuated prostate volume reduction by dutasteride. *EurUrol* 2013; 63: 1115–21.
22. Ford, E. S., Giles, W. H. & Dietz, W. H. Prevalence of the metabolic syndrome among US adults: findings from the third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *JAMA* 28 7,356–359 (2002).

24. Maserejian, N. N. et al. Treatment status and progression or regression of lower urinary tract symptoms in a general adult population sample. *J. Urol.* 2014; 191: 107–113.
25. D. S. Prasad, Z. Kabir, A. K. Dash, Prevalence and risk factors for metabolic syndrome in Asian Indians: A community study from urban Eastern India. *JCDR*; 3: 204-211.
26. Yasme Khan, Arati Lalchandani, Ajesh Chandra Gupta, Prevalence of metabolic syndrome crossing 40% in Northern India: Time to act fast before it runs out of proportions, *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2018; 7:118-23.
27. Cruz F, Desgrandchamps F. New concepts and pathophysiology of lower urinary tract symptoms in men. *Eur Urol Suppl* 2010; 9: 472–6.
28. Moul S, McVary KT. Lower urinary tract symptoms, obesity and the metabolic syndrome. *Curr Opin Urol* 2010; 20: 7–12.
29. Parsons JK, Sarma AV, McVary K, Wei JT. Obesity and benign prostatic hyperplasia: clinical connections, emerging etiological paradigms and future directions. *J Urol* 2009; 182: S27–31.
30. Rohrmann, S., Smit, E., Giovannucci, E. & Platz, E. A. Association between markers of the metabolic syndrome and lower urinary tract symptoms in the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III). *Int. J. Obes. (Lond.)* 2005; 29:310–316.
31. Eom, C. S. et al. Metabolic syndrome and accompanying hyperinsulinemia have favorable effects on lower urinary tract symptoms in a generally healthy screened population. *J. Urol.* 2011; 186:175–179.
32. Ohgaki, K. et al. Association between metabolic syndrome and male lower urinary tract symptoms in Japanese subjects using three sets of criteria for metabolic syndrome and International Prostate Symptom Score. *Urology* 2011; 77: 1432–1438.
33. Gacci, M. et al. Metabolic syndrome and benign prostatic enlargement: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BJU Int.* 2015; 115: 24–31.
34. Kristal, A. R. et al. Race/ethnicity, obesity, health related behaviors and the risk of symptomatic benign prostatic hyperplasia: results from the Prostate Cancer Prevention Trial. *J. Urol.* 2007; 177: 1395–1400.
36. Kok, E. T. et al. Risk factors for lower urinary tract symptoms suggestive of benign prostatic hyperplasia in a community based population of healthy aging men: the Krimpen Study. *J. Urol.* 2009;181: 710–716.
37. Wong, S. Y., Woo, J., Leung, J. C. & Leung, P. C. Depressive symptoms and lifestyle factors as risk factors of lower urinary tract symptoms in Southern Chinese men: a prospective study. *Aging Male.* 2010; 13: 113–119.
38. Lin PH, Freedland SJ. Lifestyle and lower urinary tract symptoms: what is the correlation in men? *Curr Opin Urol.* 2015;25(1):1-5.